

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: EBONYI****FIRST NAME: AUGUSTINE****PROGRAM CODE: DIPH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: (MSWord 2016 on Windows 10)

THE RUDIMENTS OF ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

Now that I have commenced my study for the Doctor of Philosophy in International Public Health (DIPH) with EUCLID and having gone through the period one study materials, I have come to better understand how very critical academic writing is. Besides, it suddenly dawned on me that academic writing at the Doctor of Philosophy (Ph.D.) level is a little more complex than I had earlier thought, but nevertheless very exciting. This is against the backdrop of my having previously studied for a Master of Science in Epidemiology by distance learning. As I set out to write my first response paper, I envisaged that the EUCLID study materials, EUCLID ACA-401D coursepack with the Basic ACA-401 Tutorial and Zotero training videos, will very richly educate me on the various aspects of good academic writing. Among these should be the proper use of English, encompassing the United States of America (U.S.) or United Kingdom (U.K.) English grammar. There is also the writing style including the rule of style, of which obviously the one most favoured by EUCLID is Turabian (EUCLID 2015, 53). I also expected that the materials will provide me with further insight into the ubiquitous issue of plagiarism, the various citation styles and how to maintain structure with a logical flow during writing. In this writeup, I set out to highlight the salient information I have obtained from the aforementioned study materials.

2) EUCLID COURSEPACK

This coursepack discusses the fundamentals of academic essay writing as well as some aspects of paper writing.

a) Essay writing

An essay has a number of segments. Initially, it is important to define the question or problem that needs to be answered or dealt with. The question should be used to generate a hypothesis that will be supported with evidence and examples from existing literature. At this stage, the first plan of the essay should also be made as this helps to guide how one intends to answer the question and with which relevant information. Next, comes extensive searching and reading of relevant literature. As the volume of literature that needs to be searched is usually large, the technique of skimming and scanning and perusing through the table of contents could be quite useful for the quick extraction of relevant information needed. While reading, it is important to make notes of all the evidence, knowledge and examples required to support the arguments for answering the research question or those that support the hypothesis. The arguments not in favour of the hypothesis should also be considered. Detailed bibliographies of every evidence noted in support of answers to the research question must also be collected during searching and reading (EUCLID 2015, 5). What follows is to organise the collated notes or ideas in a coherent and logical fashion into what will now form the blueprint for the first draft of the essay.

The essay's blueprint is structured into the traditional - Introduction, Body and Conclusion. The body should have paragraphs with each paragraph expressing one main idea. Each idea is first captured in the opening statement (i.e, the 'topic sentence'), followed by 'supporting sentences' explaining the idea and then the 'evidence sentences' that provide the actual evidence with examples where needed, for the idea been put forward. The paragraph is then brought to a close with a 'critical conclusion' after first analysing and interpreting in detail the evidence gathered from literature (EUCLID 2015, 4). The overall objective of the Body section is to answer the research question by means of evidence and examples through a constructive and logical argument in order to convince the reader or audience. As for the Introduction and Conclusion sections, whereas the former opens with the 'general to specifics' of the research question, the latter ends with moving from 'specific to general' (ibid.). In the former case, it means starting with a general statement followed by the hypothesis for the research question and summary of the research topic. In the latter case, it means providing the answer to the research question, recapturing the principal ideas. This is followed by making a final general statement with the potential implications of the research findings and suggestions for future research (ibid.).

Having done all of the above, the essay writing should end mandatorily with the bibliography, for which in the case of EUCLID, the referencing style is the Turabian rule of style. It is generally considered that doing a bibliography is one of the surest safeguards against plagiarism. The essay draft is not cast in stone and so should be edited severally, checking for grammar, revising sentences, formatting and ensuring a sequential flow of ideas, amongst others. Where available, a checklist is used to make sure nothing was left out, before finally submitting the essay.

b) Paper writing

This discusses some aspects of writing a good paper using an approach preferred by EUCLID. This section essentially focuses on the application of some English grammar rules in paper writing with numerous examples. This is in addition to EUCLID's recommendation of using American English and Turabian Style guide. Then there is the CRIB Sheet for the Chicago Manual of Style.

In writing a paper, great emphasis is placed on the use of correct English grammar and on avoiding plagiarism through proper citation of any piece of work or information source. Plagiarism is said to occur when either "the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information" or "having someone write a paper for you and then putting your name on it" (EUCLID 2015, 9-10). It is considered an unethical practice of monumental proportion that comes with very dire consequences. A citation has two components, in-text citations and a list of works cited also called references or bibliography. As the name implies, in-text citation involves placing the cited item within the text of a paper by means of quotation or paraphrases. Whereas quotations could be long or short and are the author's exact words, paraphrases are the original ideas of the author structured and written in the writer's own words. However, in situations where the ideas/ information are well known empirical facts or are well known in the public domain, a citation is not necessary. The bibliography which comes at the end of a paper gives the publication details of the work being cited. It can take different forms depending on whether it is a book or a journal article and if it is an online work or not. In contrast to bibliography, footnote referencing which also comes in-text is listed at the bottom of each page, that is, the 'footnote area' of the paper. Also, its referencing format is slightly different from that of the bibliography. Zotero can be used for both bibliography and footnote referencing and is more versatile than Word in this regard (EUCLID, 2016a).

The Chicago style of writing in the context of research papers is another connotation for the Turabian style of writing. This style is detailed in the CRIB Sheet and most of these have been discussed above. In my opinion, this sheet should be a companion of any 'Writer' or 'Essayist'.

c) Educational videos

The tutorial video showed me how to format a document in the specially designed EUCLID Word template and how to use the various Styles on this document for preparing both response and major papers (EUCLID, 2016b). In contrast, the Zotero video focuses on the use of Zotero with Word, for referencing, bibliography and footnotes. It also showed how to use the Word template for EUCLID assignment purposes (ibid.).

3) CONCLUSION

The EUCLID study materials and this response paper which I have prepared have given me a practical understanding of the rudiments of writing an academic paper. I have learned that in writing a paper or essay, it is not enough to have research ideas through reading or other means but that it is important to structure/ organise these into the traditional essay with an Introduction, Body, and Conclusion. While in the introduction the ideas will be formed into a research question or hypothesis, the body strives to answer the questions through argument by means of evidence and examples from literature all of which must be cited and referenced to safeguard against plagiarism. A conclusion is then drawn with a statement of an answer to the research question as well as the potential implications of the research findings and suggestions for future research. Throughout the essay or paper writing, I learned that it is crucial to maintain the correct English grammar usage, to allow the ideas presented to flow logically and sequentially and to adopt a Turabian style of writing. For me, going forward with my DIPH study, these rudiments of academic writing will form one of the pillars I will need in building my expertise in academic writing which in my opinion is really one of the cardinal features of a Ph.D. study.

REFERENCES

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